

Emotion to the Invisible: Historic Landscape Formation of the A-bomb Dome

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Abstract

This paper aims to analyze the transformation of a historical landscape that has been formed centering around the A-bomb Dome, the creation of its values and the emotions that form the basis of such values, and to establish how the surrounding environment should be designed. First, the author analyzes characteristics of the spatial configuration of the A-bomb Dome and the formation process of the landscape's social values. Secondly follows an analysis of changes in tour-guide routes as well as the content of guidance provided on various sightseeing tours that started after World War Two, so as to examine the transformation in emotional responses that has occurred in relation to this landscape. In conclusion, the author discusses the design of the public information board near the building which touches upon the lost environment (the invisible) in its immediate surroundings.

Conference theme: Values and Culture

Keywords: historic landscape, sightseeing tours, A-bomb Dome

Introduction

Non-verbal emotion comprises our physiological, social and psychological reactions, and it can be, at the same time, a historical reaction. Especially, in this day and age when urban environmental design based on the principle of environmental conservation is becoming mainstream, it is essential that the historicity of human emotion, and the feelings connected with the historical environment, become apparent. In the case of Hiroshima, in particular, the potential to remember and inherit all human emotions relating to being bombed and to share “Hiroshima” with others as a historical present always remains under consideration. It concerns the sustainability of emotion as general theme.

This paper thus aims to analyze the transformation of a historical landscape that has been formed centering around the A-bomb Dome (the former Hiroshima Prefectural Industrial Promotion Hall), the central and iconic facility located in the bombed Hiroshima, and emotional responses leading to the creation of its values, and to establish how the surrounding environment should be designed. It is true that values of landscapes are influenced not only by emotional responses but also by social contexts. However, values of landscapes that are not based on emotional responses cannot be sustainable.

Among previous research works, those studied using the system of the peace museum to preserve negative memories (Williams, 2007) or those that analyzed the architectural and social significances of the A-bomb Dome of the day as a “heritage” (Ogino, 2002; Moore, Whelan, 2007) can be found. However, there are still no such works that study the emotional responses which make the basis of landscape value formation and their historical changes from the perspective of their relation to the immediate surroundings.

Method

First, the author illustrates characteristics of the spatial configuration of the pre-A-Bomb Hiroshima Prefectural Industrial Promotion Hall and the landscape transformation of this former Prefectural Hall, which has been conserved to this day in its post-bombing state as the A-bomb Dome. In addition to these urban spatial analyses of the A-bomb Dome regarding the transformation in its historical landscape, the author focuses attention on sightseeing tours that started after World War Two as information sources to evoke emotional responses and analyzes tour-guide routes around the A-bomb Dome, viewing points, viewing objects and changes in explanation style and the content of sightseeing services so as to examine the transformation in emotional responses that has occurred in relation to this landscape.

In this paper, the author considers the three most common sightseeing organizations associated with the Hiroshima Peace Memorial Park: regular tour buses run by Hiroshima Bus Corporation, Hiroshima Peace Volunteers trained by the Hiroshima Peace Memorial Museum and the Hiroshima City Volunteer Guide Association in order to analyze the changes that have taken place in guiding. In comparing three sightseeing services during the period from 1999 to 2000, it became clear that the guiding routes and places visited were very similar to each other. The author thus carries out an analysis focusing on sightseeing services provided by the Hiroshima Regular Tour Bus, which provides useful documents (sightseeing textbooks) enabling one to trace the history of typical sightseeing patterns.

Various kinds of administrative documents in the collection of Hiroshima City Archives are used as primary sources. The author also uses newspaper articles and photographs (including those that have not yet been published) kept by the Chugoku Shimbun as well as sightseeing textbooks to complement them. The sightseeing textbooks are those used by bus guides working

for Hiroshima Bus Corporation, which runs regular tour buses in Hiroshima City, to learn all the guiding content by heart. These textbooks are exclusive in-house documents, produced by instructors who teach and train new bus guides. Since guidance has been basically provided according to this textbook, the author uses them as primary source for analyzing sightseeing guidance. Six sightseeing textbooks compiled in 1962, 1973, 1982, 1985, 1991 and 1999 are all looked into by the author so as to analyze changes in their sightseeing routes, viewing points, viewing objects and guiding content.

It is not sufficient to analyze the viewers' emotional response from the sightseeing textbooks, but these books are revised in response to the needs of the tourists and the citizen's feelings. It is a firm sense of mission of the agency at the place such as being bombed place.

Turning the Prefectural Industrial Promotion Hall into a place of scenic interest and the A-bomb Dome into a monument

Figure 1: Postcard of the pre-war Prefectural Industrial Promotion Hall (Source: Bombed Structures Study Group ed. 1996, p. 27)

Figure 2: The present A-bomb Dome (Source: Photographed by the author, September 1, 2006)

Figure 3: Landscape axis of the pre-war era (left) and the post-war era (right) in the Hiroshima Peace Memorial Park (by the author)

The A-bomb Dome, which was designed by a Czech architect, Jan Letzel (1880-1925), and completed as Hiroshima Prefectural Produce Museum Hall (which changed its name to Hiroshima Prefectural Industrial Promotion Hall at a later date) assumed the role of a cultural base by frequently holding product exhibitions or art exhibitions. Since the Meiji period, various facilities including commercial buildings, banks and schools, as a symbol of modernization, had been seen scattered throughout the city. The Dome had its entrance facing the Motoyasu River, and its copper doom-roof lent a high-impact profile to the city's urban landscape. The well-styled entrance hall encircled by a spiral staircase was a novelty in those days. The Dome was thus a popular sightseeing point from the start (Bombed Structures Study Group ed.1996). Especially the view of the area from the Aioi Bridge to the Motoyasu Bridge was often captured in postcards, etc, as a public landscape (Figure 1).

A plan to demolish the Dome as a hazardous building was once put under consideration as the remedial plan after World War Two advanced. But, in the Peace Memorial Park Plan by a

Japanese architect, Kenzo Tange (1913-2005), which was finalized in 1949, this destroyed Industrial Promotion Hall was regarded as a central element of the park and its continued existence bore a monumental significance (Tange, Fujimori, 2002). Around that time, people began to call it the A-bomb Dome. After World War Two, new perspectives and axes of vision of the building as a monument in a peace memorial park were generated. (Figure 2) (Figure 3)

Around the A-bomb Dome, makeshift shacks were gradually taken away and new high-rise buildings began to appear. However, in 1960 when a new Chamber of Commerce building was constructed on the north side of the Dome, there was little consciousness of conserving the A-bomb Dome and only its dark colors rather than the height of this structure standing on the axis came to be an issue. In the 1960's, though there were some debates over the conservation of the A-bomb Dome, which was fast weathering, as to whether the Dome should be conserved as memory of the war or should be demolished as it evoked the atomic bombing disaster, the first conservation operation was carried out in 1967 and the second one in 1989. Meanwhile, a skyscraper was constructed in a deregulated area as part of the redevelopment project in Moto-machi near the A-bomb Dome. However, with the momentum of urban revitalization, the scene of this towering hotel revealing itself behind the A-bomb Dome was never really argued over (Hiroshima Prefecture , 1989).

Figure 4: Buffer zone pertaining to listing the A-bomb Dome as a World Heritage Site (Source: Hiroshima Prefecture, 1997. p. 37)

It is also true that the A-bomb Dome, designated as a World Heritage site in 1996 (the official name is the Hiroshima Peace Memorial), managed to have a buffer zone established by not legally restricting the vested interests of residents living in the vicinity of the Dome while seeking the ideal of conserving the Dome including its immediate environment (Hiroshima Prefecture, 2006)(Figure 4). As a result, it has ended up creating such a cityscape around the Dome with lots of apartment buildings standing close together. In other words, the A-bomb Dome constitutes a pocket-park closed landscape. Why this issue has not been taken up by society could be to do with Japanese spirituality. It may be, at the same time, a matter of habituation with the landscape or a matter of emotion's real-time nature (or sustainability). As above, the peace landscape of the A-bomb Dome has not been formed by one-dimensional ideology only. Diverse values opposing or conflicting with each other, are found up to the present date regarding the landscape of the A-bomb Dome amid the historical process of modernization, war damage and post-war recovery. However, as a consequence, emotional responses to the landscape of the A-bomb Dome isolated from rapidly developing environs are likely to become limited.

Sightseeing Routes

On regular sightseeing bus tours, the A-bomb Dome is shown around as part of a visit to Hiroshima Peace Memorial Park. Their sightseeing routes stay the same throughout the year: Tourists get off a bus after they cross over the Aioi Bridge as they look from onboard at the A-bomb Dome on their left, are guided to walk southward through the park, and get on a bus again on the south side of Hiroshima Peace Memorial Park (Figure 5). It is possible to see the

symbolic view of the A-bomb Dome from the Memorial Cenotaph to the A-Bomb Dead that is located in almost the center of the Peace Memorial Park. But usually tourists do not get off a bus and look closely at the Dome except during their free time. Direct and immediate explanation about the A-bomb Dome is provided from the other side of the Motoyasu River (Figure 6).

Figure 5: Sightseeing routes in the Peace Memorial Park after 1999 (by the author)

Figure 6: The A-bomb Dome and sightseeing in 1962 (above-left), 1973 (above-right) and 1985 (below) (by the author)

The northern route across the former Nakajima Hondori Street (Motoyasu Bridge-Honkawa Bridge) directly connected to the A-bomb Dome that runs in front of the Children's Peace Monument went straight southward through the center of the Park for twenty years from 1962 to 1982. After 1985, this northern route changed to pass along the Motoyasu River in order to go via the A-bomb disaster information board after 1985, which makes the whole route longer. Furthermore, from 1999 onward, tourists have been guided to go east and west in order to visit various monuments on the northern route.

The sightseeing route changed from the straight one going southward from a disembarkation point to the one going south while moving around east and west by walking along the Motoyasu River and the Memorial Monument after 1985. This change in the sightseeing route can be attributed to the increase in the number of installed objects that can be a viewing point and the riverbed improvement work carried out in the Motoyasu River in 1982 as part of Hiroshima city's "Urban beautification campaign."

Viewing Points

Viewing points straight to the A-bomb Dome are unchanged: while aboard a bus, after getting off a bus and on the other side of the Motoyasu River.

Looking into changes in specific viewing points on the north side of the park, one of the points by the disembarkation point (map symbol: b) does not have any viewing objects nearby.

According to the description in the guiding textbook, time is allocated on this point for tourists to take photographs with the A-bomb Dome on the opposite riverbank in the background.

However, in guidance after 1982, this spot disappeared from the lists of viewing points.

Instead, the A-bomb disaster information board (map symbol: d) was placed in 1980 on the opposite bank from the A-bomb Dome and the information board itself has become one of the guided viewing points since 1985. This viewing point is very close to another point near the disembarkation point (map symbol; b), so there has been no period when these two points “d” and “b” existed simultaneously. The A-bomb disaster information board has “replaced” the disembarkation point as a viewing point.

Viewing Objects

The main viewing objects on the north side of the Park have been the A-bomb Dome and the Aioi Bridge, the target of the atomic bomb, in each period, and the number of viewing objects including monuments installed in the Park increased. In sightseeing guidance provided after 1985, the A-bomb disaster information board placed on the riverbank across from the Dome itself joined the list of viewing objects. Since the period when this information board became a viewing object , the Motoyasu River and various buildings standing outside the Park have also become viewing objects and the scope of the object distribution has thus expanded. With the increase of objects placed in the park, the number of viewing objects in the delta of the Nakajima district has also risen. On top of this, with the installment of the A-bomb disaster information board, viewing objects outside the Park increases and the scope of the view has thus expanded in the north side of the Park.

Explanation Style

On the north side of the Park, in tourist information services provided from 1962 to 1982, the

number of viewing points increased on the sightseeing route after disembarkation from the bus. The positional relation between viewing spots and viewing objects is mostly either identical or adjacent to each other and the explanation style is thus mostly on a one-to-one basis: one viewing spot to one viewing object. Most viewing objects are located within the delta in the Park and tourists are guided to this viewing point to receive relevant explanation about the object. Therefore, at the times when a viewing point and a viewing object were closely located to each other, the viewing direction and scope from a viewing point were limited, as the relevant object was in the foreground. In this context, a viewing spot near the disembarkation point was the point where tourists could look at the A-bomb Dome standing on the other side of the river and was thus the only viewing point with an outward view.

However, after 1985, the style in providing information at viewing points changed drastically in two ways. One difference is that the information board was newly put into place at the viewing spot so that relevant explanation could be provided on multiple objects from there. This information board is placed against a background of the Dome with the photograph of the Prefectural Industrial Promotion Hall, which shows how the A-bomb Dome used to look like before the A-bomb was dropped. This information board not only makes a temporal comparison of the A-bomb Dome by providing explanation about how the Dome used to be and how it is now but also gives explanations of various objects to be seen in various directions and distances from there. Therefore, the information board is equipped with two functions: The board itself is an object like other memorial monuments, and at the same time is a viewing point to provide information about other viewing objects.

Another difference is that after 1985, implicit and evocative explanation was added when a relevant explanation was provided at the A-bomb disaster information board. The board touches upon Shima Surgical Hospital at the hypocenter as well as the floating-lantern festival on the

Motoyasu River. That is, this information board not only provides a comparative explanation contrasting with how the Dome used to look in the past but also is endowed with a sense of time that explains what one can presently see or what one used to be able to see. Styles of providing information on the north side of the Park have become diversified with the placement of the A-bomb disaster information board and the scope of objects to be seen also broadened. Furthermore, the board evokes tourists' emotional responses to the historical environment.

Guidance Content

Map symbols	Viewing point	Viewing Targets					
		1962 (Showa 37)	1973 (Showa 48)	1982 (Showa 57)	1985 (Showa 60)	1991 (Heisei 3)	1999 (Heisei 11)
a	Aioi Street	A-bomb Dome Aioi Bridge	Hiroshima Chamber of Commerce Industry A-bomb Dome Aioi Bridge	Hiroshima Chamber of Commerce Industry A-bomb Dome Aioi Bridge	A-bomb Dome Aioi Bridge	A-bomb Dome Aioi Bridge	A-bomb Dome Aioi Bridge
b	Disembarkation	A-bomb Dome	A-bomb Dome				
c	Peace Clock Tower		Peace Clock Tower	Peace Clock Tower	Peace Clock Tower	Peace Clock Tower	Peace Clock Tower
d	Atomic Bomb Disaster Information Board (Hiroshima Prefectural Industrial Promotion Hall)				Atomic Bomb Disaster Information Board (Hiroshima Prefectural Industrial Promotion Hall) A-bomb Dome Aioi Bridge Hypocenter·Shima Surgery Motoyasu River (Floating-lantern festival) Monument to Tamiki Hara War Memorial to the Mobilized Student	Atomic Bomb Disaster Information Board (Hiroshima Prefectural Industrial Promotion Hall) A-bomb Dome Aioi Bridge Hypocenter/ Shima Surgery Motoyasu River (Floating-lantern festival)	Atomic Bomb Disaster Information Board (Hiroshima Prefectural Industrial Promotion Hall) A-bomb Dome Aioi Bridge Hypocenter/ Shima Surgery Motoyasu River (Floating-lantern festival)
e	Peace Bell		Peace Bell	Peace Bell	Peace Bell	Peace Bell	Peace Bell
f	Atomic Bomb Memorial Mound	Atomic Bomb Memorial Mound	Atomic Bomb Memorial Mound	Atomic Bomb Memorial Mound	Atomic Bomb Memorial Mound War Memorial to Atomic Bomb Victims Who Died Violent Death	Atomic Bomb Memorial Mound War Memorial to Atomic Bomb Victims Who Died Violent Death	Atomic Bomb Memorial Mound War Memorial to Atomic Bomb Victims Who Died Violent Death
g	Monument in Memory of the Korean Victims of the A-bomb						Monument in Memory of the Korean Victims of the A-bomb
h	Gravestone Exposed to radiation (Gravestone in the remains of Jisenji Temple)						Gravestone Exposed to radiation (Gravestone in the remains of Jisenji Temple)
i	Children's Peace Monument	Children's Peace Monument	Children's Peace Monument	Children's Peace Monument	Children's Peace Monument	Children's Peace Monument	Children's Peace Monument

Table 1: Viewing objects from the viewing spot on the north side of the Peace Memorial Park

(by the author)

		Viewing Targets					
		A-bomb Dome	Aioi Bidge	Hypocenter	Monument to Tamiki Hara	Memorial Tower to the Mobilized Students	Floating-lantern festival
Before the installation of the information board	1962 (Showa 37)	(Explanation provided while a bus is making a stop.) "Please look on your left hand side. The building that is mirroring the reflection of its run-down image is the former Hiroshima Prefectural Industrial Promotion Hall designed by a German architect and constructed in 1915 (Taisho 4). As we recall, it was seventeen years ago, on August 6, 1945 (Showa 20), at 8:15 in the morning when ordinary citizens' frugal life in Hiroshima was just about to begin. The world's first atomic bomb exploded at an altitude of 570 meters over Hiroshima and"	(Explanation provided while a bus is running) "The bridge that we are approaching is the Aioi Bridge. Hiroshima, the city of water, is also known for its numerous bridges. This bridge is, as you can see, a very unique one with its T-shape. The river on your right is the Hon River and the Motoyasu River on your left."				
	1973 (Showa 48)	(Explanation provided while a bus is making a stop) "Please look on your left hand side. The building that you see over there is coming into the view was the former Hiroshima Prefectural Industrial Promotion Hall constructed in 1915 (Taisho 4) upon the design of a Czech architect. As we recall, it was seventeen years ago, on August 6, 1945 (Showa 20), at 8:15 in the morning when ordinary citizens' frugal life in Hiroshima was just about to begin. The world's first atomic bomb exploded at an altitude of 570 meters over Hiroshima and こころ中心に..."	(Explanation provided while a bus is running) "The unique T-shaped bridge that we are crossing over shortly is the Aioi Bridge."				
	1982 (Showa 57)	(Explanation provided while a bus is making a stop) "Please look on your left hand side. The building that you see over there is coming into the view was the former Hiroshima Prefectural Industrial Promotion Hall constructed in 1915 (Taisho 4) upon the design of a Czech architect. As we recall, it was seventeen years ago, on August 6, 1945 (Showa 20), at 8:15 in the morning when ordinary citizens' frugal life in Hiroshima was just about to begin. The world's first atomic bomb exploded at an altitude of 570 meters over Hiroshima and"	(Explanation provided while a bus is running) "Beyond the Chamber of Commerce and Industry, there is the T-shaped Aioi Bridge, very unique even in Japan. You will see the A-bomb Dome on the riverbank on the east of the bridge."				
After the installation of the information board	1985 (Showa 60)	"Is everybody here? Let me introduce you to some of them. Please look at this information board. This is the former Hiroshima Prefectural Industrial Promotion Hall, how the A-bomb Dome used to look like. The Hall was completed in 1915 (Taisho 4) upon the design of a Czech architect, Jan Letzel. It was a very modern building with the green dome on top but the world's first atomic bomb exploded at an altitude of around 580 meters at 8:15 in the morning on August 6, 1945..."	"Now, everyone. Please look on your left. The T-shaped Aioi Bridge that we have crossed over earlier is a symbol of the center of the city. This bridge can be easily found from the sky and that is why it was used as the target of the atomic bomb..."	<i>"Now about 240 meters away from the Aioi Bridge, we can see Shima Surgery Hospital diagonally forward right... Can you see? ...it is said that the atomic bomb exploded at an altitude of 580 meters over the Hospital..."</i>	<i>(Moving over slightly) "There is a monument inscribed with a poem written by Tamiki Hara from Hiroshima City in the shade on the right of the A-bomb Dome..."</i>	<i>"Next, there is a five-storied tower on your right. Can you see? That tower is called "Memorial Tower to the Mobilized students..."</i>	<i>"once every year, on the evening of August 6, floating-lantern festivals are quietly held on rivers including this Motoyasu River in the city..."</i>
	1991 (Heisei 3)	"Is everybody here? Let me introduce you to some of them. Please look at this information board. This is the former Hiroshima Prefectural Industrial Promotion Hall, how the A-bomb Dome used to look like. The Hall was completed in 1915 (Taisho 4) upon the design of a Czech architect, Jan Letzel. Built with brick, it was a very modern building with the green dome on top but the world's first atomic bomb exploded at an altitude of around 580 meters at 8:15 in the morning on August 6, 1945 and"		<i>"In this direction, there is Shima Surgery Hospital. It is generally said that the A-bomb Dome was the hypocenter. However, accoring to previous research findings, the exact hypocenter is now believed to have been at an altitude of 370 meters over the Hospital, located 160 meters southeast of the A-bomb Dome..."</i>			<i>"Once every year, on the evening of August 6, floating-lantern festivals are held on rivers including the Motoyasu River in the city and pray for the souls of the dead"</i>
	1999 (Heisei 11)	"Is everybody here? Let me introduce you to some of them. Please look at this information board. This is the former Hiroshima Prefectural Industrial Promotion Hall (built for the purpose of promoting the industry in Hiroshima), how the A-bomb Dome used to look like. The Hall was constructed in 1915 (Taisho 4) upon the design of a Czech architect, Jan Letzel. Built with brick, it was partly a five-storied modern building with the green dome on top, but the world's first atomic bomb exploded at an altitude of 580 meters over Hiroshima at 8:15 in the morning on August 6, 1945 (Showa 20)."		<i>"In this direction, there is Shima Surgery Hospital. It is generally said that the A-bomb Dome was the hypocenter. However, the exact hypocenter was at an altitude of 580 meters over the Hospital, located 160 meters southeast of the A-bomb Dome..."</i>			<i>"Once every year, on the evening of August 6, floating-lantern festivals are held on rivers including the Motoyasu River in the city and pray for the souls of the dead"</i>

Table 2: Contents explained on the A-bomb disaster information board (by the author) (Note: Explanation written in Italic is for those invisible)

Viewing objects that are expected to be explained at the viewing point on the north side of the Park are shown by period in Table 1. As for installed objects including monuments, explanation is provided at a one-on-one level. However, with the placement of the A-bomb disaster

information board, the number of viewing objects has risen sharply. Guidance contents explained on the board are shown by viewing object in Table 2.

According to Table 2, guidance content is divided into two groups: that whose content changed after the installment of the A-bomb disaster information board, and newly that for newly joined viewing objects. Looking into the guiding content explaining the A-bomb Dome in the former group, until 1982 the information was provided on the bus about the A-bomb Dome, including the name of the pre-A-bomb Dome and its architect, the circumstances of the atomic bombing, and the background and the history of the former Hiroshima Prefectural Industrial Promotion Hall's turning into the A-bomb Dome. On the other hand, the information board presents a summary of the former Hiroshima Prefectural Industrial Promotion Hall using the pre-A-bomb photograph. It further provides information about the disastrous state when the A-bomb was dropped and the process of how the building was conserved as the A-bomb Dome. By giving relatively detailed accounts while comparing and contrasting the pre-A-bomb photograph with the present A-bomb Dome, one clear time axis that continues from the pre-A-bomb state to the post-A-bomb state and then to this day is thus generated.

Varying in viewing direction as well as distance, newly added viewing objects have expanded the scope of the view. Though the building of Shima Surgical Hospital at the hypocenter is now invisible, the guidance provided on the information board indicates the direction and reads as follows: "The hypocenter was at 580 meters above Shima Surgical Hospital, which was located 160 meters southeastward from the Dome." Also, by the Motoyasu River, the explanation is given about the floating lantern festival that is annually conducted on August 6, which is another implicit and evocative explanation among many. Viewing objects from this viewing spot were especially numerous in 1985. There has an attempt to provide more guidance from the explanation board viewing point for the A-bomb Dome viewing objects on the opposite bank,

where it was not possible to disembark.

Since the A-bomb disaster information board itself became one of the viewing spots, viewing objects that have continued to be explained are: the A-bomb Dome, the hypocenter and the Motoyasu River (the floating lantern festival), and the information about the festival is provided after the A-bomb Dome and the hypocenter are explained. The floating lantern festival originated in the prayers for the victims of the bombing, so the time axis from the pre-A-bomb state to immediately after the bombing and then to the post-A-bomb state is also found in the order of guidance.

This way, the guidance provided on the spot where the A-bomb disaster information board is in place gives comparative explanation between the pre-A-bomb and the present states, and explains respective viewing objects located in various directions and distances following the time axis, from the pre-A-bomb state and immediately after the bombing, on to the present.

Conclusion

The A-bomb Dome as a testament to the A-bomb survivors has grown “isolated” from its developing environs and become an edifying monument symbolizing the anti-war and nuclear-free movements. As a result, diverse emotional responses are vanishing. The author believes that it must be connected to the fact that the buffer zone set at the time of the world heritage listing is not working, and that the conversion of the surrounding environs to high-rise buildings is advancing.

In contrast with such a social context, from the time that the information board with the photograph of the former Prefectural Industrial Promotion Hall was placed on the riverbank across from the A-bomb Dome in the Peace Memorial Park, volunteers’ and tourist agents’

emotions toward the historical environment from the past have been strongly stirred. Though the information board may simply provide the information to explain the structure, it also touches upon the lost environment in its immediate surroundings. That is, the A-bomb Dome was the sole evidence of the history of nuclear bombing before the board was put in place, though picturesque souvenir photographs may be taken there. The information board now evokes the imagination of businesspeople who are aware of the importance of the past toward the area surrounding it, which is now developed and the past evidence of which is being obliterated, and our non-verbal emotion toward the invisible is beginning to work. The board must also be influencing tourists' emotions as well. The information board was put in place in order for the government to inherit the memories of bombed building structures and to explain historical facts. (There are 45 information boards installed within five kilometers of the hypocenter in Hiroshima city.) Generally considered, tourists should find meaning in confirming historical facts and evoke the past in their imagination.

Going beyond the government's intent, the imagination of those who see the site would extend to its immediate landscape and further to the invisible historical landscape. A historical continuity is being perceived in cityscapes that one is seeing now. It is true that evoking historical environs in the past may have a limit to it as long as the information remains suggestive. It may be such emotion stretching out to the immediate landscape; however, that saves the A-bomb Dome from historical fragmentation in the social context, in the form of a lesson about the 20th Century, and guarantees the historical continuity of the place.

It does not mean that information boards can be installed anywhere. The Prefectural Industrial Promotion Hall was originally designed as a structure that looked out onto the river, and the site where the board is now in place has been a very important location to look at the building from since the time when it was named and used as the Prefectural Industrial Promotion Hall. The

historical significance of the location of the board has an influence on the intensity of emotional responses evoked. Not only conservation and restoration of historical structures but also more comprehensive design taking into account the history of a place enriches our emotion to the invisible.

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